

Professor's Experiences in Reflective Portfolio for Materials Engineering Program

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Abstract

In Brazil, on April 24, 2019, the Ministry of Education issued Resolution CNE/CES No. 2, unveiling major revision National Curricular Guidelines for undergraduate Engineering Programs. These revisions aim to modernize course curricula and enhance the preparation of future engineers, with a focus on essential skills and competencies. In fields like Health Sciences Education, teachers have utilized Reflective Portfolios to showcase achievements alongside personal and professional development. This is accomplished through critical reflection on evidence derived from their experiences. This paper aims to analyze and discuss the implementation experiences of both teachers and students regarding Reflective Portfolios, while also exploring their impact on student learning. Spanning 15 weeks during the second semester of 2023, the study was conducted with students at Fluminense Federal University registered in the Thermoplastic Processing of Material Engineering Program. The students were tasked with submitting reflective portfolios, discussing the learning acquired during the course, to a fictional company, which could use this document in the selection process. The development of skills and competencies acquired through the implementation of reflective portfolios was assessed using quantitative methods such as the Friedman test, along with qualitative analysis of open-ended responses. Findings suggest that students perceived themselves as highly proficient in their skills and competencies; however, according to the quantitative study, no significant differences were discerned in their performance or grades throughout the course duration. The study concludes that, although significant advancements in skills and competencies may not be perceived within the study period, their value lies in cultivating self-awareness and facilitating experiential learning. Despite the need for further investigation, the study advocates for the ongoing utilization of reflective practices in engineering education to nurture holistic student development.

Keywords: Reflective Portfolio; Material Engineering; Skills; Competencies; Engineering Education.

1 Introduction

In Brazil, on April 24, 2019, the Ministry of Education issued Resolution CNE/CES No. 2, unveiling major revision National Curricular Guidelines for undergraduate Engineering Programs (Brasil, 2019). These revisions, along with Resolution CNE/CES No. 1/2021, aim to reform course curricula and enhance the preparation of future engineers, with a focus on essential skills and competencies (Brasil, 2021). Considering the significance of skills and competencies for engineering students, providing opportunities for reflective practices is essential, as they serve to promote the development of students in these areas.

Given 'reflection' denotes the cognitive process enabling the conversion of experience into personal knowledge by bridging emotional and cognitive states, the incorporation of reflective practice should mirror the student's individual contemplation regarding the efficacy of their learning. The reflective portfolio serves as a tool for reflective practice, enabling teachers and students to develop a comprehensive understanding and facilitating a more efficient assessment of their learners' knowledge and skills (Efe, 2016).

Reflective portfolios are collections of evidence that, through critical reflection, highlight achievements alongside personal and professional growth. They usually contain written evidence detailing both learning outcomes and processes. By providing a critical analysis of their contents, portfolios serve as tangible evidence of achievement and personal/professional development (Plaza, Slack, Skrepnek & Sauer, 2007). Reflection is a

fundamental aspect of a portfolio, along with the student-teacher relationship and clear guidelines for portfolio construction (McMullan, 2003).

The students demonstrate ongoing acquisition of skills, knowledge, attitudes, understanding, and achievements, rendering it a dynamic record of growth and professional evolution. Reflective Portfolios encompasses both retrospective and prospective elements, reflecting the current stage of individual development and activity. Moreover, it effectively communicates the qualities, competencies, and abilities of the owner, while also indicating potential areas for development. Another advantage of implementing Portfolios in the course is the reinforcement of learning. The reflective component can provide this link between theory and real professional practice, thereby helping to reduce the 'reality shock' experienced by many students when they transition into practice (McMullan, 2003).

In fields such as Health Sciences Education, educators have embraced Reflective Portfolios as a means to showcase their achievements and foster personal and professional development. This process involves critical reflection on evidence drawn from their experiences, facilitating insights, practice refinement, and ongoing development, often within the context of patient care (Plaza, 2007; Cordeiro & Silva, 2020). In the realm of engineering, this approach has been integrated with project-based work, contributing to enhanced graduate abilities in articulating thoughts and sharing experiences with peers, professionals, and the public (Helwig, Simmons, & Goh, 2019). Carroll and colleagues' approach (2007) involved transferable skills through both individual and collaborative reflective learning, all facilitated by open-source software developed by the team (Carroll, Markauskaite, & Calvo, 2007).

In higher education in engineering, one widely used tool is the Electronic Portfolio (e-portfolio), which are a web-based information management system that utilizes electronic media and services. This system offers a dynamic, flexible, and interactive way to document academic and professional progress. In this context, it is essential to have platforms that host these portfolios, such as Mahara, PebblePad, and Foliotek. E-portfolios can also be utilized to maintain transparent records for learning pathways, credit transfers, and various modes of participation and assessment (Alam, Chowdhury, Kootsookos & Hadgraft, 2015). In Brazil, the study of e-portfolios as a pedagogical tool within the engineering curriculum, particularly in Engineering in Industrial Design and Product Development, demonstrated that these new teaching and learning models in higher education institutions could be implemented to facilitate the teaching of technical subjects through the English language. (Polyakova, Juliá-Sanchis, Galstyan-Sargsyan & Galstyan-Sargsyan, 2023)

Initial testing of portfolios with engineering students is important to ensure the successful implementation of this methodology in any educational program. After the method proves successful, incorporating technology into portfolios can significantly enhance learning outcomes. This paper aims to analyze and discuss the experiences of both teachers and students using Reflective Portfolios. It will also explore the impact of these portfolios on student learning, skill development, and competency acquisition within the materials engineering student body at Fluminense Federal University, Brazil. Through this analysis, the study seeks to provide insights and recommendations for the broader application and integration of Reflective Portfolios in engineering education.

The Materials Engineering program at the Federal Fluminense University (UFF) is based in the interior of Rio de Janeiro state, specifically at the School of Industrial Metallurgical Engineering of Volta Redonda (EIMVR). Commencing in the second semester of 2018, the Materials Engineering course admitted 20 students per semester, culminating in its inaugural graduating class in 2023. In the same year, the curriculum underwent revision with the introduction of a new Pedagogical Project of the Course (PPC). This initiative aimed to update the competencies and skills required by students, fostering the development of engineers capable of

addressing contemporary societal and industrial challenges with creativity and responsibility, while considering human, social, technical, and ethical dimensions (Universidade Federal Fluminense, 2018).

The professional disciplines within the program are structured into four knowledge tracks: Materials Science and Engineering, Metallic Materials, Ceramic Materials, and Polymeric Materials. Reflective portfolios were introduced for third-year Material Engineering students, particularly within the Polymeric Material track, focusing on Thermoplastic Processing. This course aimed to equip students with an understanding of fundamental thermoplastic polymer processing techniques, enabling them to determine material types, processing methods, and suitable operational conditions for specific product production.

2 Methodology

2.1 Procedure

The students were encouraged to create their portfolios based on a proposal for a fictional company, as described below:

"You are participating in the selection process for the position of Engineer at a renowned company specialising in the commercialization of thermoplastic processing equipment. In the final stage of the selection process, the company provided a comprehensive course on Thermoplastic Processing, through which candidates will be evaluated via a reflective portfolio."

Subsequently, the students received a tutorial on how to construct the Reflective Portfolio and followed the instructions outlined below:"

1. It was recommended to use a presentation program.
2. The Portfolio should begin with a self-description, addressing questions such as: Who am I? Where do I come from? How do I intend to contribute to the company?
3. The essential concepts related to the theme were to be included in the Portfolios, used texts, images, audio, video, links, or paper.
4. Finally, students were required to reflect on what they had learned. This section of the Portfolio should address questions such as: What have I learned from this activity? What challenges did I encounter and how did I overcome them? How has this experience contributed to my personal and academic development? How can I apply what I have learned in the future?

To ensure the quality of the portfolios, students are given the opportunity to review their work and make any necessary corrections before evaluation.

2.2 Evaluation

The Reflective Portfolios were evaluated throughout the semester by both professors and students based on the following criteria: Knowledge, Reflection, Creativity, Layout, and Essay. These criteria are scored on a scale from 0 to 100, with ratings of Excellent, Good, Average, and Poor. The portfolio grade was determined as an average of the assessments provided by the teacher and the student. However, in cases where the disparity between the grades exceeded 30%, the student's grade was adjusted to align closely with the teacher's assessment.

The self-assessment of skills and competencies for students is conducted on a scale from 10 to 0, encompassing the following dimensions: Analysis and Problem Solving, Oral and Written Communication, Technical Knowledge, Socio-environmental Awareness, Creativity, Results Interpretation, Leadership, Strategic Planning, Punctuality and Attendance, Proactivity, Decision Making, and Teamwork. The students can provide

suggestions and comments regarding the strengths and weaknesses of their skills and competencies through open-ended responses.

2.3 Data Analysis

To describe the distribution and variability of portfolio grades data, various statistical measures were computed, including the average, median, and standard deviation to evaluate the performance of ten students. The data were collected in the second semester of 2023 during the Thermoplastic Processing course in the undergraduate Materials Engineering program.

The development of skills and competencies acquired through the implementation of reflective portfolios was assessed using non-parametric analysis, such as the Friedman test. This test was employed to ascertain any variations or distinctions among research variables across thematic progressions. Specifically, the statistical theory under examination is outlined as follows:

- Null Hypothesis (H0): The mean ranks of variables are equal, indicating no difference in performance among students' self-assessment of their skills and competencies across thematic progressions.
- Alternative Hypothesis (H1): The mean ranks differ significantly, indicating differences in performance among students' self-assessment of their skills and competencies across thematic progressions.

The significance level for this hypothesis testing is set at $\alpha = 0.05$. H0 is rejected if $p < \alpha$. These non-parametric analyses were conducted using jamovi software version 1.6.23 under a free license (<https://www.jamovi.org>).

Furthermore, qualitative analysis was conducted on open-ended responses. The question posed was: "Identify a competency or skill that stood out in the development of this section of the Portfolio and provide justification for its assessment rating."

3 Results and discussion

Portfolio Assessment

According to the professor, the significant challenges encountered during portfolio implementation included the absence of reflective components in student activities, students failing to submit the complete portfolio, and discrepancies between the assessments of the professor and the students. These challenges manifested in fluctuations in the average grades across the semester's themes, as depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. Grade of course along of semester.

Themes covered during the Thermoplastic Processing course								
	Polymer	Rheology	Processing	Extrusion	Injection Molding	Other Processing	Additives	Blends
Average	77.8	70.8	72.0	65.5	57.5	61.3	60.8	70.3
Median	79.0	70.5	72.0	69.5	68.0	61.5	65.0	66.5
Standard deviation	5.0	5.3	0.8	15.5	28.9	18.9	19.8	12.6
Minimum	71.0	65.0	71.0	44.0	15.0	38.0	33.0	60.0
Maximum	82.0	77.0	73.0	79.0	79.0	84.0	80.0	88.0

Although the majority of average grades for the themes exceeded 60 points (the minimum grade requirement for passing the course), the overall average was not as high, due to lower scores in the reflection item and lack

of creativity in the Portfolios. While the maximum grade improved in the last themes compared to the first, the worsening of the minimum suggests that while the top-performing students have made strides, many students still find it hard to achieve the learning goals.

In the case of the Injection Molding and Additives, the data distribution is asymmetric, as indicated by the significant difference between the average and median. This result, along with the minimum value of 15, suggests that some students with lower scores are pulling the average down.

The lower scores of these students were attributed to deficiencies in reflection, creativity, and the absence of certain items in their portfolio submissions. Regarding reflection, the lower scores were mainly due to two factors: firstly, students rarely engaged in reflective practices during the engineering course; secondly, they lacked self-awareness. Despite receiving training on portfolios and feedback from the professor, students found it challenging to incorporate meaningful reflection into their work. As for creativity, it demands dedication and time to innovate, which resulted in grade variations based on this criterion. Consequently, some students couldn't allocate enough time to their portfolios due to commitments to other courses throughout the semester, leading to the absence of some items in their portfolio submissions.

Self-assessment of skills and competencies

Figure 1 illustrates the average perceptions of students regarding their performance in technical knowledge and creativity. These self-assessment serves as a tool to exemplify students' perceptions of their skills and competencies during the implementation of themes in course of Thermoplastic Processing.

Figure 1. Students' perceptions of their skills and competencies

The results of Figure 1 revealed that students perceive these skills (technical knowledge and Creativity) to be highly proficient, with performance scores exceeding 70. However, the thematic progression in the course did not seem to reflect such advancements in their expertise. In essence, they did not detect any enhancement in these skills as they already assessed them to be above the anticipated level. To validate potential significant differences in students' self-assessment of their skills and competencies throughout the semester, the Friedman test was employed. Table 2 show the results of the Friedman test concerning the skills and competencies identified by students within their portfolios.

Table 2. Result of Friedman Test.

Skill and competence	p-value
Oral and Written Communication	0.309
Technical Knowledge	0.154
Creativity	0.075
Results Interpretation	0.113
Strategic Planning	0.035
Punctuality and Attendance	0.128
Proactivity	0.083
Decision Making	0.080

The skills and competencies, such as Analysis and Problem Solving, Socio-environmental Awareness, Leadership, and Teamwork, are absent from this table because students considered that these skills and competencies were not involved in the construction of portfolios.

All evaluated skills and competencies show values higher than 0.05, indicating no significant difference in performance among students' self-assessment of their skills and competencies across thematic progressions. Consequently, the skills and competencies at the end of the course were considered equal to those at the beginning of the course, as assessed by the students.

According to literature the students have difficult to mark realist grade when they do self-assessment. Brown and Harris's (2014) research sheds doubt on the efficacy of self-assessment as an evaluation method, emphasizing the importance of certain conditions for students' judgments to be deemed useful, valid, and reliable. And the Chur-Hansen (2001), said that the students' uncertainty about their ability to grade because mainly the difficult to be objective and no experience in grading/uncertain about standards. Then, the professors of this research presented another set of questions to the students, this time focusing on open-ended inquiries about competencies and skills. These open-ended questions revealed some general insights presented in Table 3.

The students recognize the need to enhance their skills to diverge from the conventional. The improvement by applied Reflection Portfolio is exemplified by the Selected Raw Data of Creativity, where students evaluated their skills in the themes "Polymer" (the initial theme) and "Additives" (nearly the final one). It is evident that they recognize their progress in their work, which is also apparent in their perception of Technical Knowledge and Reflection. However, they also acknowledge the potential for further refinement in these skills.

Despite the Friedman test indicating that students did not improve these skills or competencies, the open-ended questions revealed that students acknowledged improvement in these areas. They were capable of evaluating their progress and demonstrated responsibility for their advancement. This phenomenon is known as self-regulation. The utilization of self-assessment within assessment for learning policies relies on theories of self-regulated learning, which recognize that students can improve their self-regulation skills through self-assessment, students set targets and evaluate progress against criteria, thereby enhancing their accountability for tracking their progress (Brown, Gavin & Lois Harris, 2014).

Table 3. Responses from students to open-ended questions regarding competencies and skills

Skills and competences	Theme	Selected raw data
Creativity	Polymer	<i>"I believe it is necessary to express my creativity in other ways so that the portfolio stands out compared to more conventional presentations."</i>
	Additives	<i>"A very creative portfolio, however, I believe it should include more technical knowledge to better delve into the subject."</i>
Technical Knowledge	Rheology	<i>"The technical knowledge required to interpret the behavior described in the graphs relating to the samples."</i>
	Extrusion	<i>"Technical knowledge - It was one of the deliveries with the most detailed information."</i>
Reflection	Polymer	<i>"I was able to explain the topics well, but I had difficulty with reflection."</i>
	Extrusion	<i>"From the extrusion portfolio, I did all the reflections, which had been a challenge until then. I believe this is a positive point."</i>

This study of reflective portfolios for the Materials Engineering Program presented several limitations, such as a small group of students involved, a large volume of portfolio submissions that hindered quick feedback for the students, the significant time investment required from both professors and students, and the students' lack of maturity in conducting self-assessment. Based on this experience, future projects will involve planning to reduce the number of portfolio submissions, providing guidance on self-assessment, and expanding the implementation of reflective portfolios to more courses within the Materials Engineering program. Additionally, future research should compare the effectiveness of reflective portfolios with traditional assessment methods in terms of promoting student learning and competency development. It should also investigate how the use of reflective portfolios can contribute to preparing students for the job market in the field of Materials Engineering, and how the implementation of platforms for e-portfolio usage can help facilitate teaching

4 Conclusion

The results of Reflective Portfolios for students in the Thermoplastic Processing courses of the Materials Engineering Program at Fluminense Federal University indicate that although significant advancements in skills and competencies may not be perceived within the study period through Friedman Test, their value lies in cultivating self-awareness and self-regulation. Despite the need for further investigation, the study promotes the continuous use of reflective practices in engineering education to foster holistic student development.

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